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On the prospects of derating and tailoring large offshore turbines for use in floating applications in sea basins with moderate wind speeds

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Abstract. Floating wind technology enables the expansion of offshore wind into deep waters, including moderate-to-low wind speed basins. Currently, these regions are underserved by western manufacturers, who have historically optimized designs for high-wind sites. Deploying these high-power machines in a low-wind environment is capital-inefficient, as the high rated capacity drives up structural costs yet remains largely underutilized. This study explores the potential of derating state-of-the-art offshore wind turbines for applications in lower speed regions. By reusing existing rotor designs with less powerful generators, the generator, drivetrain and tower can be adapted to the less demanding operating conditions. The engineering effort is also kept more manageable by reusing existing rotors. Results show that this approach can reduce capital expenditure significantly (-12.8% to -25%). These reductions are, however, met by corresponding reductions in Annual Energy Production, generally leading to an increase in levelized cost of energy. Nevertheless, the absolute economic differences are modest. Ultimately, the results suggest that carefully balancing generator power and rotor size may allow manufacturers to offer tailored, lower-risk solutions for emerging offshore markets without the need to develop new rotors from scratch.

1. Introduction

Among the potential new markets for Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) are sea basins with moderate to low wind speeds. Current offshore turbines offered by western manufacturers (OEMs) typically feature high specific power values — i.e., the ratio between rated turbine power and rotor area — often exceeding 330 W/m^2 . In fact, while a trend of decreasing specific power has been ongoing in the last two decades in the onshore market [1], it has yet to be observed in offshore wind turbines. Deploying these standard turbines in low-wind regions can be capital-inefficient; the high rated power drives up structural loads and cost, yet is rarely utilized. While developing new low-wind rotors could decrease Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE), it requires significant investment and risk. This is especially the case for FOWTs, which have not entered commercial production yet. Nevertheless, FOWTs are uniquely positioned to exploit the advantages of specific power reduction. Since platform movement causes additional inertial and gravitational loading on the structural components [2], lowering aerodynamic loads permits lighter components, which inherently reduces the inertial forces acting on the structure. This mechanism can lead to significant cost reductions, though the extent of this benefit is debated [3].

To this end, this study explores the potential advantages of derating state-of-the-art offshore wind turbines for applications in lower speed regions. The generator, drivetrain, and tower of the turbines are tailored to the lower peak power output, while the rotor blades are left unchanged.

This pragmatic approach enables the adaptation of offshore turbines for the less structurally demanding operating conditions, while maintaining the engineering effort more manageable. The tower, in particular, is a critical component in FOWTs. Land-based and offshore bottom-fixed wind turbines are typically designed to be *soft-stiff*, i.e., the first natural frequency is placed in the gap between the 1P and 3P excitation bands. This strategy is difficult to replicate with floating designs for three main reasons: 1) floating installation increases ultimate and fatigue loading on the tower due to gravitational and inertial loads [2]; 2) the gap between 1P and 3P excitation bands is reduced due to the slow rotational speed of offshore rotors; 3) floating installation causes the tower natural frequencies to increase, often pushing a soft-stiff tower's first natural frequency into the 3P range. As such, FOWT towers are typically designed to be *stiff-stiff*, where the first natural frequency is placed above the 3P range. In this scenario, derating the wind turbine reduces the rotational speed of the rotor and thus decreases the 3P excitation frequency, relaxing the stiff-stiff constraint. Additionally, as previously mentioned, a reduction in rated power results in a corresponding decrease in the aerodynamic loads acting on the tower.

In this context, the opportunities and challenges associated with derating a FOWT are evaluated using two open-access reference turbines, the IEA-22MW reference wind turbine (RWT) [4] and the IEA-15MW RWT [5], which represent the current state of the art in academic research. Although they are both originally designed for the Atlantic Ocean (Gulf of Maine), this study considers an installation site in the Mediterranean Sea, which was considered representative of an installation site with less demanding metocean conditions and lower wind speeds. The performance of each of the two reference turbines is evaluated under various derated power levels, achieved by reducing both the rated rotational speed and the rated rotor torque. More specifically, the IEA-22MW RWT is considered with power values of 22 MW, 15 MW, and 10 MW, while the IEA-15MW RWT is evaluated with rated powers values of 15 MW, 10 MW, and 8 MW. For each rated power level, the turbines are redesigned using a Multi-Disciplinary Design and Optimization (MDAO) tool. The resulting designs are critically compared in terms of overall structural mass, dynamic performance, Annual Energy Production (AEP) and LCoE.

2. A systems-engineering approach

The opportunity for cost reduction of offshore wind turbines when derating is performed is evaluated by redesigning the generator, the drivetrain and nacelle, and the tower sequentially. The floater and the mooring lines are left unchanged with respect to the reference wind turbine that each derated turbine is derived from. As such, all the investigated turbines feature four-column semi-submersible floaters, which are anchored to the seabed using three catenary mooring lines [4,5]. This section will detail the approach that was followed in each design step.

2.1 Generator design methods

All the turbines compared in this study feature a direct-drive permanent magnet, synchronous, radial flux generator, which features an inner stator ring with a series of copper coils, and an outer rotor, which houses a series of permanent magnets. The electro-magnetic interaction between the magnets and the coils generates the output current and voltage. A preliminary electro-magnetic and structural design is performed using GeneratorSE [6]. Nine design variables are optimized, the stator tooth height (h_t), the number of electromagnetic poles (pp), air gap diameter (D_a) and width (l_s), the stator and rotor yoke thickness (h_{ys} , h_{yr}), the magnet height (h_m), the number of turns per coil (N_s), the armature current density (J_s) and the stator tooth width (b_t). These parameters are used to create a 2D cross-sectional geometry which is evaluated using the open

access Finite Element Method Magnetics (FEMM) solver [7] to determine the magnetic field. The electromagnetic performance is then determined using conventional magnetic circuit laws [8]. Electromagnetic losses are also computed using analytical loss formulations. The structural sizing is carried out based on a simplified geometry of the system and exploits analytical formulations. In this design effort four structural variables are considered, the stator and rotor yoke thickness (h_{ys}, h_{yr}) and the stator and rotor disk thickness (t_s, t_r). Electromagnetic and structural optimizations are performed sequentially. From a structural perspective, the main constraints are the radial deformation of the rotor disk and rim, and stator disk and rim, which are each allowed to deflect up to 8.5% of the 7 mm air gap.

Figure 1. Diagram of the generator and drivetrain. Drivetrain and generator overview (a) with generator (orange) and drivetrain (blue) geometric parameters. Azimuthal slice of IPM generator section (b).

2.2 Drivetrain and nacelle design methods

The drivetrain for the direct-drive turbines compared in this study is designed using DrivetrainSE, a core-component of the system-level design tool WISDEM [9]. A diagram showing the structure of the nacelle is shown in Fig. 1. DrivetrainSE uses a series of empirical and analytical equations to estimate the size of the main drivetrain components and the weight and cost of the main nacelle components. Seven design variables are considered in this study, the low-speed shaft diameter and thickness (D_{ISS}, t_{ISS}), the nose diameter and thickness (D_n, t_n), the thickness of the bedplate (t_{BP}) and the distance from the first main bearing to the nose (L_1) and between the two main bearings (L_{12}). A combination of a Compact Aligning Roller Bearing (CARB, upwind) and a Spherical Roller Bearing (SRB, downwind) are considered to sustain radial and axial loading. In addition to geometric constraints on nose and rotor shaft length, a maximum stress constraint is imposed on the rotor, nose and bedplate. A maximum radial deflection constraint is also imposed for stator, which is allowed to deflect up to 2.5 mm at the generator stator attachment, and the rotor, which is also allowed to deflect radially 2.5 mm. Reaction forces, stresses and strains are derived in DrivetrainSE through PyFrame3DD by modeling the rotor and the nosecone and bedplate as one-dimensional beams. Weights of the nacelle housing, cooling system, power electronics, and other ancillary components are instead estimated through empirical relations, as described with more details in [10]. The optimal values of the design variables are found through an optimization targeting the minimization of nacelle mass.

2.3 Tower design methods

The towers of the de-rated turbines are designed with an optimization routine aimed at minimizing tower mass. In all the presented cases, the towers are redesigned to achieve first structural frequencies (f_1) at least 20% higher than the corresponding maximum 3P frequency. For the IEA-22 MW RWT with a power rating of 22 MW, this results in a 45% increase in the first natural frequency (f_1) with respect to the reference design. In fact, the tower of the IEA-22MW RWT has not been redesigned for floating application and its first natural frequency is within the 3P range. This tower design has been acknowledged to be too light, and a redesign has been planned¹. All optimizations are performed with consistent constraints on buckling, maximum stress, taper, slope and local thickness to diameter ratio. The tower's natural frequencies are computed within WISDEM by modeling the tower through a series of beam elements in the finite element solver PyFrame3DD with concentrated masses and inertias at the tower top to include the effects of the rotor and nacelle assembly and at the tower bottom, in order to include the floater mass and hydrodynamic added mass. Loads are estimated within WISDEM considering steady-state aerodynamic loads, hydrodynamic pseudo-static loads computed with strip theory, and gravity loads. WISDEM approximates extreme aerodynamic loading using an equivalent gust defined as $U = \bar{U} + n\sigma$, where $\sigma = TI \cdot \bar{U}$. Upon preliminary comparison with loads from time domain simulations, this study uses $n = 5$ to conservatively increase the estimated aerodynamic loads, thereby also accounting for the additional loads induced by FOWT motion. The optimization algorithm chosen for this purpose is COBYLA [11].

2.4 Performance and techno-economic analysis

The performance of the redesigned FOWTs is evaluated using the non-linear time domain simulation tool QBlade [12]. A Normal Sea State (NSS) [13] corresponding to a site west of Sicily (Italy) is considered, with a Class III wind speed distribution. Additional information on the met-ocean conditions of the site can be found in [14], while the procedure to derive such conditions is described in more detail in [15]. Six distinct turbulent wind seeds are employed for each mean wind speed, each simulated for 1000 s to ensure statistical convergence. More in detail, aerodynamics are solved using QBlade's Blade Element Momentum (BEM) module and structural dynamics are solved using a flexible multi-body approach. The floater is modelled as a rigid body, and hydrodynamics are solved using a potential flow approach, augmented with additional quadratic damping in the case of the IEA-15MW and strip-theory drag for the IEA-22MW as explained in [5] and in [4], respectively. Finally, the mooring cables are modelled using a dynamic cable model implemented within QBlade and based upon the Project::Chrono engine [16].

As for the LCOE estimation, the Capital (CAPEX), Operational (OPEX), Development (DEVEX) and Abandonment (ABEX) expenses are computed using a variety of methods, which are briefly described in the following. The CAPEX of the rotor, drivetrain (generator excluded) and tower are estimated using the DTU cost model, modified for application to FOWTs in [17]. More in detail, the mass of these components is computed using WISDEM, and the relations described in [17] are used to correlate the mass and cost of the various components. Generator costs are instead estimated directly in GeneratorSE, as explained more in detail in [8]. For raw material expenses, the same cost factors reported in [18] are used. Additional costs are included for the HVAC system, labor and capital needed to construct the component, as detailed in [6]. Floater costs are instead estimated using the relations described in [19], based on the mass of the floater's columns and pontoons, which is estimated in WISDEM. OPEX, DEVEX and ABEX are estimated using the DTU cost model. However, the nominal power of the respective rotor designs (i.e. 22 MW for the 284 m

¹ [https://github.com/IEAWindSystems/IEA-22-280-RWT/wiki/Frequently-Asked-Questions-\(FAQ\)](https://github.com/IEAWindSystems/IEA-22-280-RWT/wiki/Frequently-Asked-Questions-(FAQ))

rotor and 15 MW for the 240 m one) are used in place of turbine rating for OPEX estimation as a conservative estimation. The metric adopted to assess the economic viability of wind turbines is the Simple Levelized Cost of Energy (sLCOE). This metric, originally defined in [20] represents a simplified formulation of the conventional LCOE, where financing aspects, discounting effects, and future replacement or degradation costs are neglected. Moreover, sLCOE assumes constant AEP over the entire project lifetime, as well as constant annual OPEX. It is further assumed that the total CAPEX is incurred entirely at time $t=0$, with no additional investment during the operational lifetime of the power plant. Under these assumptions, the sLCOE can be computed as in Eq.1:

$$sLCOE = \frac{(CAPEX + DEVEX) \cdot CRF + OPEX + APEX}{AEP} \quad (1)$$

where the CRF (Eq. 2) is the Capital Recovery Factor which expresses the ratio of a constant annuity to the present value of receiving that annuity for a given length of time and is defined as function of the discount rate r (8%) and the number of lifetime years n (35):

$$CRF = \frac{r(1+r)^n}{(1+r)^n - 1} \quad (2)$$

3. Results

The main outcomes and implications of the component redesigns performed in this study are shown in Table 1. The influence of derating on component design, starting from the generator and then moving to the drivetrain and tower are further discussed in Section 3.1, where a selection of the most relevant results is shown. The main outcomes of the load analysis as well as techno-economic considerations are instead discussed in Section 3.2. The redesigned wind turbines are identified by the combination of rated power and rotor diameter, e.g., the 10-240 turbine refers to a 10 MW machine that uses the 240 m diameter rotor designed for the IEA 15 MW RWT.

Table 1. Main parameters of the redesigned turbines compared in this study. AEP is computed using a Class III wind speed distribution.

	IEA 22 MW – D = 284 m – TSR = 9			IEA 15 MW – D = 240 m – TSR = 9.15		
Power (MW)	22	15	10	15	10	8
Specific Power (W/m ²)	347.3	236.8	157.9	331.6	221.6	176.8
RNA mass (t)	1266.989	1203.266	1141.986	1036.475	862.379	852.209
Tower mass (t)	3046.481	1679.019	1359.495	1316.322	1012.630	911.778
Tower cost (k€)	8834.79	4869.16	3942.54	3817.33	2936.63	2644.16
Total CAPEX (k€)	71394.29	59485.65	53362.67	49791.39	43391.82	41483.08
ΔCAPEX (%)	n/a	-16.68	-25.26	n/a	-12.85	-16.68
AEP (GWh/yr)	77.621	64.62	50.953	53.321	43.932	38.437
ΔAEP (%)	n/a	-16.75	-34.357	n/a	-17.61	-27.91

Figure 2. Generator cost (a), mass (b), design electromagnetic torque (c) and efficiency (d) as a function of rated power for the two rotors compared in this study.

3.1 Generator design

The generators for the turbines compared in this study were designed with the procedure discussed in Section 2.1. The procedure was applied to the baseline IEA-15MW and IEA-22MW rotors as well in order to fairly compare them to the de-rated versions. As discussed in Section 2.1, the design procedure involves solving the magnetic field on a 2D slice of the generator at each iteration. As discussed in [8], this causes noisy gradients, and a challenging design space to navigate for an optimizer as a result. Therefore, the gradient-free algorithm COBYLA [11] is used. Nevertheless, some extra steps were necessary to ensure that the final designs are fully comparable. Starting from the respective reference turbine (either the IEA 22 MW or the IEA 15 MW) the generators are optimized first for efficiency.

The result is used as a starting point for the subsequent optimization, which targets to minimize cost from a feasible design point. For this step, the (D_a) and width (l_s) were removed from the optimization, as the optimizer may tend to reduce them to reduce cost, at the expense of electromagnetic torque. For the cost-optimization, a lower bound on efficiency was set to 94.5% for all designs. The main outcomes of the optimization are shown in Fig. 2. Reducing the nominal rating of the IEA 22MW RWT allows for cost savings of approximately 1 M\$ when reducing power to 15 MW and an additional 1 M\$ when further reducing to 10 MW. Similar cost reductions are found when derating the IEA 15 MW, with generator cost reduced by over 1 M\$ when reducing rated power to 10 MW. The de-rated generators for the IEA 15 MW are generally lighter and less costly than the generators designed for the IEA 22MW at the same power rating due to the higher operating speed of the smaller rotor and thus the reduced torque requirements (Fig. 2c).

3.2 Nacelle and drivetrain design

The inputs to the design procedure described in Section 2.2 are the generator characteristics in terms of dimensions, weight and efficiency and the design aerodynamic loads, which are derived from preliminary aeroelastic simulations. These simulations are identical to the final load analyses, the results of which will be discussed later on in this study, but are performed on the unchanged reference IEA-15MW and IEA-22MW RWTs. With respect to the reference machines, the rated power and rotational speed only were changed. The main results of the drivetrain optimizations are shown in Tab. 1. Despite the derated generators of the IEA 22MW being of similar weight as the 22 MW generator, and, in the case of the 15-284 generator, actually being even heavier (Fig. 2b), the reduction in peak aerodynamic load (shown later on in Figs. 4 and 5), allows for a moderate reduction in overall nacelle weight. Nacelle mass reductions are more significant for the 240 m diameter rotor, as generator mass is reduced by up to 100 t when rated power is decreased (Fig. 2b).

3.3 Tower design

The main characteristics of the optimized tower designs for the IEA 15-240 rotor and the IEA 22-284 rotor are shown in Fig. 3. The lower bound on the tower first natural frequency as well as the maximum diameter to thickness ratio proved to be design driving for both rotors. In this study a maximum diameter-to-thickness ratio of 300 is considered. Higher ratios generally lead to improved stiffness to weight characteristics for tubular steel towers, but also make manufacturing challenging [21]. The value chosen herein is in-line with previous academic studies, where values ranging from 160 [18] to 500 [22] have been used, and also correlates well to values that have been reportedly used in onshore wind turbine towers on the field [23]. Furthermore, according to [21], conventional manufacturing and transport limits give typical $D/t \sim 300$. The ratio of computed and maximum allowable limits on global [24] and shell buckling [25] as well as stress are

shown in Fig. 4. All tower designs respect these limits with some reserve margin to spare, corroborating the feasibility of the designs. The reduction in mass and cost that are achieved through the redesigns are shown in Tab. 1. Derating the 22-284 FOWT nets a reduction in tower weight of approximately 45% when rated power is reduced to 15 MW and 55% when rated power is reduced to 10 MW, causing an equal relative reduction in tower cost. Derating the 15-240 rotor on the other hand, nets lower improvements in tower cost. In this case, reductions in tower mass are approximately 23% when rated power is decreased to 10 MW and 31% when decreased to 8 MW. The large differences in tower weight for the 284 FOWT are explained by the very heavy tower design of the 22-284 FOWT. In fact, a significant increase in wall thickness (Fig. 3g) was necessary for the 22-284 FOWT to meet the constraint on natural frequency. In this regard, increasing the maximum tower diameter, currently set to 10 meters for all designs, could allow to decrease the weight while still meeting the +20% 3P frequency constraint. Increasing the tower diameter, however, may still be necessary, despite manufacturing challenges, if the current scaling trends continue.

Figure 3. First natural frequency of the floating tower (a, e), outer diameter (x-axis) as a function of tower height (y-axis) (b, e), wall thickness (x-axis) as a function of tower height (y-axis) (c, g) and diameter-to-thickness ratio as a function of the tower span (d, h). Results for 240 m diameter rotor (a-d) and for 284 m diameter rotor (e-h).

Figure 4. Ratio of maximum computed and allowed global buckling (a), shell buckling (b) and stress (c) along the tower height for the redesigned towers. Limits are computed using distributed loads corresponding to maximum tower base fore-aft bending moment in DLC 1.6.

3.4 Performance tradeoffs

Statistics of key performance metrics for the de-rated FOWTs are compared in Figs. 5 and 6 for the 240 m and 280 m rotors respectively. As shown in Fig. 5a and 6a, reducing rated power also reduces the rated wind speed. If compared to the IEC Class III Weibull distribution (mean wind speed of 7.5 m/s, shape factor 2) also shown in Figs. 5a and 6a, rated wind speed lands on the right of the distribution's peak, despite the wind speed probability still being significant at rated, especially for the lowest specific power variants. In terms of loads, a clear pattern emerges across both de-rated rotors: peak loads show a clear reduction with decreasing power levels, while standard deviations, especially the wind-speed dependent standard deviation of the tower base fore-aft bending moment (Fig 5i and 6i), remain similar when rated power level is reduced. This behavior can be explained by observing the standard deviations of nacelle fore-aft acceleration (Fig 5 and 6l) and platform pitch (Fig. 5 and 6h). In fact, both in the case of the 240 m rotor and the 280 m rotor, platform pitch shows slightly lower variation as rated power decreases, leading to lower gravitational loading. However, this is compensated by higher fore-aft nacelle acceleration, negatively impacting inertial loading. The ultimate source of the inertial and gravitational loads is wave-induced platform movement. The de-rated turbines have lower rotational inertia in pitch due to the lighter nacelles and towers, explaining the higher accelerations. For a more detailed explanation on loading sources on floating tower see [26].

From a design perspective, the very limited decrease in tower base fore-aft (F-A) bending moment standard deviation suggests that fatigue may be a limiting factor for lower specific power FOWT towers, as similar load variability is observed despite substantially reduced wall thicknesses. In this regard, re-tuning of the pitch controller and redesign of the floating platform such as the one highlighted in [27] could be beneficial.

Figure 5. Top row: mean values (solid lines), maximum values (triangles) and minimum values (reversed triangles) averaged for each wind speed bin. Bottom row: mean standard deviation as a function of mean wind speed. Generator power (a,f), aerodynamic thrust (b,g), platform pitch (c,h), tower base fore-aft bending moment (d,i), and fore-aft nacelle acceleration (e,l) for the 240 m diameter rotor.

Figure 6. Top row: mean values (solid lines), maximum values (triangles) and minimum values (reversed triangles) averaged for each wind speed bin. Bottom row: mean standard deviation as a function of mean wind speed. Generator power (a,f), aerodynamic thrust (b,g), platform pitch (c,h), tower base fore-aft bending moment (d,i), and fore-aft nacelle acceleration (e,j) for the 280 m diameter rotor.

Preliminary techno-economic metrics are instead discussed in Fig. 7, where the estimated costs and annual energy production for the different FOWTs are shown. As shown in Fig. 7a, derating the FOWTs without redesigning the floating substructure leads to an increase in LCOE for both the 280 m and 240 m rotors. The difference is steeper as specific power decreases, indicating a trend of diminishing returns. This can be explained by the sharper decrease in AEP as rated power decreases (Fig. 7a) and corresponding shallower decrease in CAPEX as nominal power decreases (Fig. 7b). In addition, the larger 280 m diameter rotor features a lower sLCOE at the same specific power of the 240 m rotor, a result which generally confirms the benefits of upscaling. In order to evaluate the possible benefits of platform redesign, sLCOE is computed for the 15-284 rotor with a 10% reduction in floater CAPEX, as if it were achieved through platform redesign. Results are shown in the green dot in Fig. 7a-c. The 10% reduction would indeed result in an sLCOE reduction with respect to the 22-284 FOWT, indicating that, if matched also with a substructure redesign, derating can indeed be a promising strategy to reduce sLCOE in moderate wind speed basins. As a final remark, it must be noted that this result is a consequence of specific assumptions and modelling choices done throughout this study. In this regard it is worth pointing out that OPEX was conservatively estimated to be constant and independent from specific power (Fig. 7d), which undoubtedly penalizes the lower specific power designs, and a fixed 10% AEP loss due to wake effects is assumed regardless of power rating. This assumption again disproportionately affects lower specific power FOWTs. In addition, sLCOE depends on the chosen wind speed distribution, which, as indicated in [17], influences the site-specific optimal specific power. Moreover, CAPEX estimates follow the methods in Section 2.4, and different cost correlations could affect the absolute sLCOE values. However, as this is a comparative study, consistent correlations are applied across all designs, reducing the impact of modelling choices. Consequently, relative differences between CAPEX, OPEX, and DEVEX may have a greater influence on the results.

Figure 7. Comparison of estimated Levelized Cost of Energy (a), Capital Expenditure (b), Annual Energy Production (c) and Operational, Development and Abandonment expenditures (d) for the 240 m and 280 m diameter rotors. The 15-284 case with 10% reduction in floater CAPEX (15-284 f90) is also shown.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a preliminary evaluation of the possible benefits, challenges, and necessary tradeoffs of derating offshore wind turbines for use in moderate sea basins is performed. In particular, the study focuses on floating wind turbines, as this technology could allow offshore wind energy to spread to lower wind speed markets. The rated power of two state of the art academic reference turbines is reduced. In the process, the generator, drivetrain, and tower are redesigned, exploiting the related benefits, such as reduced torque and rotational speed, to reduce CAPEX. The rotor is intentionally left unchanged to limit the required engineering and manufacturing effort. The floating substructure is also not redesigned, although this aspect is intended to be explored in future studies. Results show that, under the specified constraints, significant cost savings can be achieved in the generator and tower especially, with total reductions in CAPEX ranging from -12.8% to -25% depending on the specific power level and considered rotors. These decreases are met by corresponding decreases in AEP that range from -17% to -34.5% for the IEC Class III wind speed distribution considered herein. Consequently, LCOE is found to increase as specific power decreases. Nevertheless, the absolute differences in key economic indicators between configurations are often modest, suggesting that developers may still favor lower-CAPEX designs due to additional benefits such as reduced financial risk and potentially easier permitting. In addition, a 10% reduction in floating substructure cost would result in a net sLCOE benefit. Whether such a reduction is at hand requires further investigation.

From a technical standpoint, the results also highlight that meeting the frequency constraints of a stiff-stiff tower design is increasingly difficult as rotor sizes increase, thereby pushing tower heights up. If the current upscaling trends continue, increasing maximum tower diameters beyond 10 meters might be necessary. Moreover, fatigue loading in the floating tower may become increasingly critical for lower specific-power FOWTs. This effect underscores the importance of fatigue-driven design considerations in future optimization efforts. Moreover, it may bias the present results in favor of higher specific-power rotors if proven to be design driving. Notably, this behavior appears to be specific to floating offshore wind turbines, where wave-induced platform motions play a dominant role, reinforcing the need for integrated floater, controller, and tower design to fully assess the viability of derated concepts.

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